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The Development of Personal Dignity among University Students: A Socio-Psychological
Perspective

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INTRODUCTION

Relevance of the Research Topic

The concept of dignity has been examined from philosophical, legal, sociological, psychological, and pedagogical perspectives throughout history. Since the second half of the twentieth century, however, dignity has increasingly become the subject of general psychological and socio-psychological research. Personal dignity occupies a central position in human life, influencing the formation of self-concept, values, moral qualities, and attitudes, while also serving as an important determinant of behavior

The ability of young people, particularly university students, to develop self-awareness, self-realization, and a positive attitude toward themselves contributes to personal growth and psychological well-being, corresponding to the higher levels of Abraham Maslow's (1954) hierarchy of needs. The development of self-esteem and self-concept is closely associated with the formation of personal dignity. Therefore, identifying the factors that contribute to the development of personal dignity among university students constitutes an important area of socio-psychological inquiry.

Personal dignity is not only a phenomenon that shapes individuals' attitudes toward themselves but also a psychological mechanism underlying the formation of values and moral qualities. Lawrence Kohlberg's (1981) theory of moral development suggests that during adolescence and early adulthood, individuals increasingly rely on personal values and internal principles rather than external forms of social control. Consequently, personal dignity becomes more salient during this developmental period and contributes significantly to the formation of self-concept.

Contemporary technological developments and increasing dependence on digital technologies have substantially influenced young people's interpersonal relationships, educational activities, and everyday behavior. These changes have been accompanied by a gradual weakening of self-regulatory capacities and a greater reliance on external influences and social control mechanisms. Such developments may affect students' self-esteem, personal dignity, responsibility, and academic functioning, thereby highlighting the importance of investigating this phenomenon.

Furthermore, the experiences of young Azerbaijani soldiers during the 44-Day Patriotic War provide an important context for understanding the relationship between personal dignity, national dignity, and patriotism. Under certain circumstances, personal dignity and patriotic commitment may become powerful motivational forces that guide human behavior. The limited socio-psychological research on these processes further underscores the relevance of the present study.

Although individuals strive throughout their lives to preserve their dignity in the face of external pressures and challenges, not everyone succeeds in doing so. Understanding why some individuals maintain their dignity while others struggle remains a complex psychological question requiring systematic scientific investigation.

The historical prevalence of physical and psychological violence, humiliation, and violations of human dignity has led to growing scholarly and societal attention to this issue. Consequently, the protection of human dignity was recognized in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) and subsequently incorporated into the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Literature Review

Personal dignity has been approached from various theoretical perspectives. B. F. Skinner provided a socio-psychological analysis of dignity in his work *Beyond Freedom and Dignity* (1971), while Immanuel Kant examined the philosophical foundations of dignity and human autonomy in *Groundwork of the Metaphysics of Morals* (1795). Historically, dignity has been explored primarily within philosophical and legal traditions. In Azerbaijan, one of the prominent scholars who addressed dignity from a philosophical perspective was Ziyaddin Goyushov (1966).

Research Object and Subject

The socio-psychological characteristics of personal dignity.

The socio-psychological mechanisms, developmental dynamics, and influencing factors associated with the development of personal dignity among university students.

Research Aim and Hypothesis

To investigate the socio-psychological characteristics of the formation and manifestation of personal dignity among university students.

1. Personal dignity serves as a foundation for the development of other moral qualities among university students.
2. The development of personal dignity among university students is associated with the ways in which individuals perceive and represent themselves.

The study pursues the following objectives:

1. To analyze psychological, philosophical, sociological, and related literature concerning personal dignity and identify the major theoretical approaches to the phenomenon.
2. To examine the developmental characteristics and dynamics of personal dignity among undergraduate and graduate students.
3. To identify the mechanisms and directions of personal dignity development.
4. To determine appropriate methods for investigating the formation of personal dignity.
5. To empirically examine factors influencing the development of personal dignity among university students.

Methodological Framework and Methods

The study is grounded in theoretical approaches addressing the role of personal dignity in personality development, as well as its formation and manifestation. The research draws upon Lawrence Kohlberg's theory of moral development and Abraham Maslow's theory of motivation.

To investigate the socio-psychological characteristics and developmental dynamics of personal dignity, the following instruments were employed:

- Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale;
- Dembo–Rubinstein Self-Evaluation Method;
- Moral Development Assessment Method.

The study was conducted between 2019 and 2021 with undergraduate and graduate students from Baku State University, Azerbaijan Medical University, Azerbaijan Technical University, and Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University. The sample consisted of 192 participants.

Scientific Novelty of the Study

This study is among the first attempts to investigate the socio-psychological characteristics of personal dignity among university students. The research examines the relationships between personal dignity and self-attitude, self-esteem, self-awareness, self-realization, and various moral qualities.

The study identified:

- The socio-psychological nature, formation, and manifestations of personal dignity;
- The developmental dynamics of personal dignity and its characteristics among students at different stages of higher education;
- The relationship between personal dignity and moral development;
- Factors influencing the formation and manifestation of personal dignity among university students;
- The role of self-perceptions, perceived evaluations by others, and social feedback in shaping personal dignity.

Main Findings and Propositions

The study yielded the following conclusions:

- Personal dignity constitutes an important foundation for moral development and the formation of moral qualities among university students.
- The development of personal dignity is positively associated with self-esteem and self-evaluation.
- Personal dignity plays a significant role in the formation of self-concept.

Theoretical and Practical Significance

The findings contribute to the understanding of the psychological nature, developmental dynamics, and socio-psychological determinants of personal dignity. The study enriches the

existing literature on dignity and provides insights into the role of personal dignity in personality development.

From a practical perspective, the findings may be used in educational settings to promote positive self-attitudes, self-esteem, and moral development among university students. The results may also assist educators in creating supportive learning environments based on humanistic principles.

Dissemination of Findings

The findings of the study were presented and discussed at scientific seminars organized by the Department of Social Psychology of the Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences. Two scientific articles based on the dissertation have been published, while one article and one conference paper were prepared for publication.

CHAPTER 1. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF PERSONAL DIGNITY

1.1. The Psychological Nature of Personal Dignity

The concept of dignity has been examined from philosophical, legal, sociological, psychological, and educational perspectives throughout history. Since the second half of the twentieth century, dignity has increasingly attracted attention within psychology and social psychology (Anthony, 2014; Donnelly, 2009; Kant, 1785; Pols et al., 2018). Human dignity plays an important role in human life, influencing the development of self-concept, values, moral qualities, and attitudes, while also guiding individual behavior.

The term *dignity* originates from the Latin word *dignitas*, meaning worthiness, honor, or esteem. In ancient Rome, dignity was closely associated with social status, nobility, prestige, and public recognition. Individuals who demonstrated self-control, moral virtue, and socially valued conduct were considered worthy of respect and honor (Donnelly, 2009). Consequently, dignity was initially understood as a characteristic primarily attributed to members of the social elite rather than as a universal human quality.

Contemporary perspectives, however, conceptualize dignity as an inherent human value. In many philosophical and psychological approaches, dignity is understood as an intrinsic worth possessed by every individual regardless of social status or personal achievements (Azərbaycan dilinin izahlı lüğəti, 2016).

One of the earliest thinkers to address the concept of dignity was Marcus Tullius Cicero (1913). In his work *On Duties*, Cicero argued that human beings possess a unique moral responsibility derived from their capacity to distinguish right from wrong (Gurbuz, 2012). Dignity, therefore, was closely linked to human rationality and moral responsibility.

The philosophical foundations of dignity were further developed by Immanuel Kant (1785). According to Kant, dignity is an inherent value that belongs to all human beings. Unlike material values, dignity cannot be measured, exchanged, or compared because it possesses absolute worth. Kant argued that dignity is rooted in human autonomy—the capacity to act according to moral principles rather than external pressures or personal desires.

Autonomy enables individuals to regulate their own behavior and make moral decisions independently. For Kant, human dignity is inseparable from autonomy, as autonomous individuals are treated as ends in themselves rather than as means to achieve the goals of others (Kant, 1785). Consequently, the ability to act freely and responsibly constitutes one of the fundamental foundations of personal dignity (Simpson & Weiner, 1989).

From a broader philosophical perspective, dignity has been regarded as a fundamental value grounded in the equal worth of all human beings and the unique status of humanity among living beings. Several philosophers have argued that human dignity does not depend on external achievements, social status, or recognition by others, but arises simply from being human. In this view, every person deserves respect by virtue of their humanity alone (Anthony, 2014).

Personal dignity can be understood from both intrinsic and relational perspectives. From an intrinsic perspective, dignity refers to the value individuals possess simply by virtue of being

human, regardless of their social status, abilities, achievements, or the admiration of others. In this sense, dignity represents an inherent value that is independent of a person's goals, interests, desires, or beliefs (Sensen, 2011).

In contrast, another perspective suggests that dignity is closely associated with personal development and self-understanding. According to this view, dignity emerges when individuals establish a meaningful place for themselves in society, develop a coherent sense of identity, and achieve personal maturity. Consequently, dignity is reflected not only in self-respect and self-worth but also in the respect individuals receive from others (Parmaksızoğlu, 2018).

Despite extensive philosophical and psychological discussions, the concept of dignity remains difficult to define precisely. A central question concerns whether dignity should be viewed as a subjective psychological experience or as a relatively stable personality characteristic. In the present study, dignity is primarily conceptualized as *personal dignity*, referring to an individual's sense of self-worth, self-respect, and moral significance. However, when dignity becomes integrated into an individual's personality structure and consistently guides behavior across situations, it may be conceptualized *as a personality trait*.

Importantly, dignity cannot be examined independently of human activity and social interaction. It is expressed and maintained through interpersonal relationships and social experiences.

From a psychological perspective, personal dignity may be regarded as a higher-order moral emotion. Moral emotions reflect individuals' attitudes toward moral principles, social norms, and the behavior of others (Kohlberg, 1981). The development and expression of such emotions are influenced by cultural context, age-related factors, and levels of moral reasoning. Lawrence Kohlberg's theory of moral development illustrates how moral judgments evolve throughout the process of socialization.

Higher-order emotions emerge through the satisfaction of complex social needs. When environmental conditions support the fulfillment of these needs, positive emotional states are experienced; when they are frustrated, negative emotional states may arise. Consequently, positive emotional experiences reinforce the continued pursuit of socially significant goals and values (Seyidov & Həmzəyev, 2014).

Personal dignity is closely associated with other moral emotions, including respect, responsibility, and patriotism. It reflects the way individuals evaluate their own behavior, personal qualities, and social conduct. Although philosophers such as Immanuel Kant (1985) argued that dignity is an inherent characteristic of all human beings, the development of personal dignity is strongly influenced by social interactions and the responses individuals receive from others.

A behavioral interpretation of dignity was proposed by B. F. Skinner in *Beyond Freedom and Dignity* (1971). Consistent with his theory of operant conditioning, Skinner argued that dignity emerges through patterns of social reinforcement. According to this perspective, individuals experience dignity when their behavior is positively recognized, valued, and

reinforced by others. Thus, dignity is not viewed as an entirely internal phenomenon but rather as a product of environmental influences and social feedback.

Like other emotions, personal dignity plays an important role in the formation of values, attitudes, and motivations. As a higher-order moral emotion, it contributes significantly to how individuals perceive themselves, relate to others, and interpret social reality.

Muzafer Sherif defined social values as standardized orientations that regulate individuals' preferences, interpersonal relationships, and the ways in which they satisfy their fundamental needs. Values play a central role in human behavior, although the hierarchical organization of values differs across individuals (Sherif, 1936).

According to B. F. Skinner, value judgments are not determined by objective facts themselves but by individuals' emotional reactions and attitudes toward those facts. These reactions are shaped by reinforcement processes. Events that produce rewarding consequences tend to be evaluated positively, whereas those associated with punishment or negative consequences are evaluated negatively (Skinner, 1971).

This perspective can be illustrated through a simple example (Bayramov & Əlizadə, 2009). Two individuals may react differently to the same rainfall. One may welcome the rain because it alleviates drought and benefits agriculture, whereas another may dislike it because it causes inconvenience. Thus, the subjective value assigned to an event depends largely on its perceived consequences and its reinforcing properties.

William James (1890b) argued that emotions are not merely consequences of physiological reactions but are closely connected to them. Building upon this idea, Skinner (1971) suggested that people do not experience positive feelings because an event is inherently valuable; rather, events become valuable because they have been associated with reinforcement. Consequently, reinforcement processes contribute to the formation of values, attitudes, and needs.

In general, people tend to classify objects, events, and experiences as "good" or "bad" according to their reinforcing effects. Values that evoke the strongest emotional responses typically occupy the highest positions within an individual's value hierarchy. Among such values are self-respect, social respect, and self-actualization.

From the perspective of trait theory, dignity may also be understood as a personality characteristic rather than solely as a subjective feeling. In this context, dignity as a personality trait refers to a relatively stable disposition characterized by self-respect, moral integrity, responsibility, and socially valued conduct. Individuals who possess dignity as a personality trait tend to demonstrate consistency in their values, principles, and behavior across different situations.

The foundations of trait theory were established by Gordon Allport (1968), Raymond Cattell (1943), and Hans Eysenck (1947). Trait theorists argued that individuals differ from one another because of relatively stable personal characteristics that influence behavior across situations. Characteristics such as extraversion, conscientiousness, sincerity, generosity, and helpfulness contribute to the explanation of human behavior.

Allport defined personality as “the dynamic organization within the individual of those psychophysical systems that determine his unique adjustments to the environment” (Allport, 1961, p. 28). One of his most important contributions was the distinction between traits, habits, and attitudes. According to Allport (1968), traits are broader and more enduring than attitudes because a single trait may be expressed across a wide range of situations and objects.

Habits may gradually evolve into personality traits through repeated reinforcement and behavioral practice. For example, behaviors initially motivated by external rewards may eventually become stable personal characteristics such as responsibility, orderliness, or self-discipline.

This distinction is particularly relevant to understanding personal dignity. Initially, personal dignity may function as a higher-order moral emotion that contributes to the development of values and moral qualities. Over time, however, dignity may become integrated into an individual's personality structure and develop into a stable personal characteristic that guides behavior across situations.

To explain this process, Allport (1961) distinguished between different categories of traits, among which cardinal traits are especially important. Cardinal traits are dominant characteristics that shape an individual's entire life, influencing behavior, values, attitudes, and personal goals. Such traits become the central organizing principles of personality and are consistently reflected in an individual's actions (Erikson, 1950).

Examples of cardinal traits include dignity, leadership, justice, narcissism, and sadism. Historical figures such as Imadaddin Nasimi, Nelson Mandela, Martin Luther King Jr., and Mahatma Gandhi are often cited as individuals whose lives were profoundly shaped by dignity and the pursuit of freedom. Their commitment to these values was consistently reflected in their actions, decisions, and social engagement.

When a particular personality trait becomes dominant in an individual's life, that person tends to seek activities, environments, and relationships that allow the trait to be expressed and reinforced. This tendency can also be observed among individuals for whom dignity as a personality trait constitutes a central aspect of their identity. Such individuals are more likely to act in accordance with their principles and values, even under challenging circumstances.

For example, the role of dignity as a personality trait may be observed in the actions of many young people who voluntarily participated in the Second Karabakh War. Motivated by their commitment to personal and national values, these individuals demonstrated remarkable courage, self-sacrifice, and dedication in defense of their homeland.

In addition to cardinal traits, Allport identified central traits, which represent the core characteristics that define an individual's personality. Although relatively few individuals possess a cardinal trait, most people can be described in terms of five to ten central traits that consistently influence their behavior. According to Allport, these traits are typically reflected in descriptions provided by close friends, relatives, and acquaintances. Examples include responsibility, aggressiveness, kindness, generosity, and jealousy.

Allport (1961) also distinguished secondary traits, which are less prominent personality characteristics that emerge only under specific circumstances. These traits exert a more limited influence on behavior and are often situation-dependent.

From this perspective, dignity as a personality trait may function as a cardinal, central, or secondary trait. When dignity assumes the role of a cardinal trait, it becomes a fundamental organizing principle of personality. In such cases, an individual's values, beliefs, goals, and behavioral patterns are strongly influenced by a commitment to dignity, which becomes consistently reflected in everyday actions and interpersonal relationships.

Finally, it should be noted that the growing scholarly interest in dignity has been closely associated with historical experiences of slavery, oppression, torture, humiliation, and other violations of human worth. As a result, dignity has increasingly come to be recognized as a fundamental principle underlying human rights.

Article 1 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) states that: “*All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights.*” This principle reflects the recognition of dignity as a universal and inalienable human value.

Similarly, Article 46 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan guarantees the protection of human honor and dignity. The Constitution affirms that every individual has the right to protect his or her honor and dignity, that human dignity is protected by the state, and that no circumstance may justify its degradation. It further prohibits torture, cruel treatment, degrading punishment, and non-consensual medical or scientific experimentation.

1.2. Personal Dignity and Social Control

Throughout the process of socialization, society and various social groups exert a significant influence on personality development, including the formation of personal dignity. This influence is primarily exercised through systems of social control. Social control plays an essential role in regulating behavior, interpersonal relations, and social interaction within groups.

One of the first scholars to systematically employ the concept of *social control* was the American sociologist Edward Ross. Every individual, social group, and social activity within society is subject to one or more forms of social control. Consequently, both individuals and groups may function as agents of social control.

Two major forms of social control are commonly distinguished: formal social control and informal social control.

Formal social control refers to regulatory mechanisms implemented by governmental institutions and other authorized bodies through laws, regulations, and official procedures. Its primary purpose is to maintain social order, ensure stability, and prevent conflicts of interest among different groups within society (Vahidov & Agayev, 2008).

In contrast, informal social control consists of social norms, customs, traditions, religious beliefs, public opinion, approval, and social disapproval. Unlike formal control, informal mechanisms operate through everyday social interactions and exert a powerful influence on individual behavior.

Both forms of social control may operate simultaneously within the same situation. For example, an individual who damages flowers or green spaces in a public park may encounter criticism or disapproval from bystanders (informal social control) while also receiving an official fine from park authorities (formal social control) (Chekroun, 2008).

Human behavior within social groups is regulated through social norms (Bayramov & Əlizadə, 2009). The term *norm*, derived from Latin, refers to a generally accepted rule, standard, or pattern of conduct (Azərbaycan dilinin izahlı lüğəti, 2016). According to Muzafer Sherif (1956), the psychological foundations of social norms—including stereotypes, fashions, customs, and values—emerge through interpersonal interaction and the establishment of shared frames of reference.

Through the process of *internalization*, individuals adopt the norms, values, cultural elements, and behavioral patterns of the groups to which they belong. As a result, social identity develops, enabling individuals to distinguish between their own group and other groups. This process contributes to the formation of the distinction between “we” and “they” and explains why members of the same group often display similar patterns of behavior (Kuppuswamy, 2961).

Social Identity Theory emphasizes that individuals cognitively define themselves in terms of group membership. According to Henri Tajfel (2004), individuals possess as many social identities as the groups to which they belong. Group membership satisfies the fundamental human need for belongingness and contributes to the development of self-confidence and self-esteem. Tajfel further argued that individuals often seek group membership as a means of enhancing their self-esteem and maintaining a positive social identity (Tajfel & Turner, 2004).

Individuals occupy particular social statuses and perform corresponding social roles within their groups. These roles are enacted according to socially accepted norms and expectations. Consequently, individuals continuously evaluate whether their attitudes and behaviors will be accepted or rejected by other group members.

Because social control is closely linked to social roles, different individuals may receive different reactions in the same social situation depending on the expectations associated with their respective roles. In this sense, social control may also be understood as an informal reaction indicating that a person's behavior is inconsistent with prevailing social norms (Chekroun & Brauer, 2002).

Social roles represent patterns of behavior that are considered appropriate within a particular social context (Sargent, 1951). When individuals conform to group norms, their behavior is typically approved and reinforced. Conversely, violations of social norms often trigger social sanctions, ranging from criticism and ridicule to more formal forms of punishment.

As Sherif (1936) observed, individuals often become aware of the power of social norms and values when they violate them and subsequently experience embarrassment, social disapproval, or punishment. Social sanctions serve to discourage undesirable behavior and reduce the likelihood of its recurrence. Even subtle reactions, such as criticism, laughter, or a disapproving facial expression, may function as mechanisms of informal social control.

One of Skinner's (1961) most important arguments was that dignity is inversely related to the visibility of social control. He maintained that when the causes of an individual's behavior become apparent, that individual tends to receive less social credit and recognition (Torke, 1973). Consequently, the perception of personal dignity may be diminished.

From this perspective, individuals organize their behavior in accordance with the moral, legal, and social norms of the groups and societies to which they belong. They also perform socially prescribed roles and fulfill expectations associated with those roles. According to Skinner, behavior that appears autonomous and self-directed is often influenced by environmental contingencies and mechanisms of social control.

To illustrate this idea, consider a singer performing live before an audience or a lecturer delivering a speech without relying on notes or external aids. Such performances are often perceived as authentic and are therefore highly valued by observers. In contrast, when a singer lip-syncs or a speaker relies heavily on prepared notes while attempting to conceal this fact, audiences may respond less favorably. In Skinner's terms, individuals receive less social credit when their behavior appears to depend on external supports rather than their own abilities. This social credit, in turn, influences how dignified and competent they are perceived to be by others.

Skinner (1961) further argued that social control is often concealed beneath the appearance of autonomy and personal responsibility. Individuals are encouraged to view themselves as free agents who are fully responsible for their actions and therefore deserving of praise or blame. However, according to Skinner, behavior is largely shaped by environmental influences and reinforcement histories. For this reason, he rejected the notion that personal dignity is solely an internal phenomenon rooted in an individual's inherent potential. Instead, he viewed dignity as a social construct that emerges through interactions with the environment and the responses of others (Torke, 1973).

The relationship between personal dignity and social control therefore remains complex. Skinner suggested that the more we understand the environmental determinants of behavior, the less likely we are to view individuals as entirely autonomous agents. Such a perspective challenges traditional conceptions of freedom and personal dignity.

Nevertheless, personal dignity is closely associated with self-regulation and self-control. Individuals who possess strong personal values and principles are capable of directing their behavior according to internal standards rather than external pressures. In this sense, self-control functions as a protective mechanism that enables individuals to resist undesirable social influences.

Overemphasizing social control while neglecting individual agency may lead to the conclusion that people are not responsible for their actions. If behavior is viewed solely as a product of external influences, positive actions lose much of their moral significance because they cannot be attributed to personal choice, values, or principles. Consequently, behavior that is perceived as entirely controlled by external forces is less likely to be regarded as dignified.

A simple example can be found in academic settings. A student who prepares thoroughly for an examination and achieves success through personal effort is generally respected by others.

In contrast, a student who attempts to obtain answers through unauthorized means may seek the same outcome but receives less recognition because the achievement is not perceived as the result of personal competence or self-discipline. Individuals with strong personal dignity are more likely to rely on their own abilities and regulate their behavior according to internal standards rather than situational pressures.

An additional observation made by Skinner is that individuals sometimes attempt to present externally motivated behavior as though it were freely chosen. For example, a child encouraged by parents to memorize a poem may eventually perform beyond the minimum requirement while presenting the effort as a personal choice. In such situations, individuals often seek social approval and recognition by portraying externally influenced behavior as self-determined. This tendency highlights the intricate relationship between social reinforcement, personal agency, and the experience of dignity.

The English philosopher and political theorist John Stuart Mill argued that individuals can be considered truly free and dignified when they are capable of exercising self-control and choosing appropriate courses of action in situations where inappropriate behavior is possible. According to Mill (2003), potentially harmful influences such as gambling or other temptations should not necessarily be eliminated from society. Rather, their existence provides individuals with opportunities to develop self-control and exercise personal responsibility. From this perspective, dignity emerges through the capacity to regulate one's behavior despite external temptations and pressures.

During early childhood, however, self-control is not yet fully developed, and behavior is therefore more strongly influenced by external forms of regulation and social control (Vahidov & Aǰayev, 2008). From a psychoanalytic perspective, Sigmund Freud argued that at this stage the *ego* has not yet fully developed its regulatory functions, resulting in a stronger influence of the *id* and a reduced capacity to delay gratification and control impulses.

In discussing self-control, B. F. Skinner (1961) distinguished between the *controlling self* and the *controlled self*. The controlling self, often associated with conscience or the superego, is primarily social in origin, whereas the controlled self is more closely related to biological needs and impulses. According to Skinner, the controlling self represents the interests and expectations of society, while the controlled self reflects the individual's personal interests and immediate needs. In this sense, conscience and the superego function as internalized representatives of social norms, defining what is considered acceptable or unacceptable behavior.

As noted earlier, the internalization of group norms and values during the socialization process contributes to the development of self-regulatory mechanisms. Through this process, social expectations become integrated into the individual's psychological structure and begin to regulate behavior from within.

In some cases, personal desires and needs may conflict with social norms or individual moral values. Such impulses may be redirected through the process of *sublimation*, whereby socially unacceptable desires are transformed into socially valued and culturally acceptable

forms of expression (Freud, 1948). Because sublimation facilitates conformity to social and moral standards, it is generally viewed positively by mechanisms of social control.

These considerations raise an important question: what can be said about an individual's personal dignity when that person behaves one way under observation and quite differently when external monitoring is absent? To address this question, it is necessary to consider the role of punishment and reinforcement in regulating behavior.

Skinner argued that punishment is a relatively ineffective means of social control. Rather than eliminating undesirable behavior, punishment often motivates individuals to develop strategies for avoiding detection and escaping negative consequences. Consequently, punishment may alter the visibility of behavior without necessarily changing the underlying behavioral tendencies.

This distinction is particularly relevant when considering personal dignity. For example, an individual may conform to social expectations only when under surveillance by authorities, whereas another individual may continue to act responsibly even in the absence of external monitoring. Similarly, a student may choose to complete an examination honestly despite having opportunities to cheat. Such behavior suggests the presence of internalized values and self-regulatory capacities that operate independently of immediate social control.

To better understand the relationship between personal dignity, self-regulation, and social control, it is useful to consider Lawrence Kohlberg's theory of moral development. Kohlberg proposed that children and adults actively construct their own systems of moral reasoning rather than merely internalizing external rules. According to his theory, individuals progress through qualitatively different stages of moral development, each characterized by increasingly sophisticated forms of moral judgment. This framework provides an important foundation for understanding how personal dignity develops and how individuals come to regulate their behavior according to internal moral principles rather than external sanctions.

Kohlberg's cognitive-developmental approach to moral learning emphasized the role of reasoning in the development of moral behavior (Hardin, 1978). He argued that moral conduct is acquired through increasingly sophisticated forms of moral reasoning and therefore placed particular emphasis on cognitive processes (Zitko-Peters, 1977). Similar to Jean Piaget, Kohlberg concluded that children's understanding of moral issues and their ability to formulate moral judgments develop progressively with age and cognitive maturity.

Stage 1: Preconventional Morality. At the preconventional level, children become aware of cultural labels such as "good," "bad," "right," and "wrong." However, they interpret these concepts primarily in terms of their physical consequences, such as punishment and reward, or the authority of those who enforce rules.

Stage 1.1. Obedience and Punishment Orientation. At this stage, moral judgments are based on the direct consequences of actions. Children obey rules primarily to avoid punishment rather than because they understand or value underlying moral principles. They begin to recognize that certain rules exist within the family and social environment, but they perceive

these rules as fixed and unquestionable. Consequently, the primary motivation for moral behavior is fear of punishment and the desire to avoid negative consequences.

Stage 1.2. Instrumental-Relativist Orientation. At this stage, children realize that different individuals may hold different perspectives and interests. Concepts such as fairness, loyalty, and equality are evaluated primarily from the standpoint of personal benefit. Moral behavior becomes increasingly guided by reciprocal exchange, reflected in attitudes such as "If you help me, I will help you" or "If you hurt me, I will hurt you." (Snarey & Samuelson, 2008). Thus, self-interest serves as the primary motivational force.

These early stages raise an important question regarding personal dignity. If a child behaves appropriately only because of parental supervision or fear of punishment, can such behavior be considered dignified? From Skinner's perspective, behavior that is clearly controlled by external contingencies receives less social credit because its causes are readily identifiable. However, an exclusive focus on external influences overlooks the role of internal psychological development. At this stage, children have not yet developed stable moral emotions such as justice, responsibility, or benevolence. Since personal dignity develops alongside these moral capacities, it is reasonable to conclude that personal dignity has not yet fully emerged during the preconventional stage.

Stage 2: Conventional Morality. At the conventional level, individuals place considerable importance on meeting the expectations of their family, peer group, and society.

Stage 2.1. Interpersonal Concordance and the "Good Boy–Good Girl" Orientation. Individuals seek approval from others and strive to be perceived as good, responsible, and socially acceptable. Consequently, they conform to the expectations associated with their social roles and attempt to maintain positive relationships. Moral behavior is motivated largely by the desire to be viewed favorably by both oneself and others (Hardin, 1978).

Stage 2.2. Law-and-Order Orientation. At this stage, individuals recognize the importance of social rules, laws, and institutional structures. They strive to fulfill their duties, maintain social order, and act as responsible members of society. Moral behavior is motivated by respect for authority, social stability, and the proper functioning of society. Because individuals internalize the norms and values of their social groups, personal dignity becomes increasingly associated with conformity to socially accepted standards and responsibilities.

Stage 3: Postconventional Morality. At the postconventional level, moral judgments are based on principles that individuals have consciously chosen and endorsed. Moral reasoning extends beyond conformity to social norms and reflects commitment to broader ethical principles such as justice, equality, and human rights.

Stage 3.1. Social Contract Orientation. Individuals recognize that laws and social rules generally serve the welfare of society, yet they also acknowledge that certain circumstances may justify exceptions. The well-known Heinz dilemma illustrates this reasoning: saving a human life may, in some situations, be considered more important than strict adherence to the law. Although social control remains important, behavior guided by deeply held values and moral convictions represents a particularly significant expression of personal dignity.

As Tamotsu Shibutani (1961) observed, what individuals choose to do—or refuse to do—is closely related to their level of self-respect. When individuals refrain from actions that conflict with their moral values despite personal desires or external pressures, they demonstrate an important manifestation of personal dignity.

Stage 3.2. Universal Ethical Principles Orientation. At the highest level of moral development, individuals construct their own moral principles independently of social approval or legal requirements. Values such as justice, equality, and human rights become paramount. Even when these principles conflict with existing laws or social expectations, individuals remain committed to defending them.

At this stage, behavior is guided primarily by internalized values and stable personality characteristics rather than external rewards, punishments, or social expectations. Historical figures such as Nelson Mandela and Martin Luther King Jr. exemplify this level of moral development through their unwavering commitment to justice despite persecution and personal sacrifice.

Kohlberg's theory provides important insights into the nature of personal dignity. The progression through higher stages of moral development suggests that dignity gradually evolves from a moral emotion into a relatively stable personality characteristic. As individuals increasingly regulate their behavior according to internal principles rather than external controls, dignity becomes integrated into their personality structure and serves as a guiding force in their actions.

Notably, the postconventional stage often emerges during adolescence and early adulthood, a developmental period characterized by advances in self-awareness, identity formation, and moral reasoning. As personal dignity becomes more firmly established, individuals become increasingly sensitive to issues of respect, humiliation, injustice, and personal autonomy. Although external treatment by others may affect an individual's sense of dignity, those who possess a strong sense of personal dignity are often capable of preserving their self-respect even in the face of social rejection, humiliation, or adversity (Əliyev, 2006). Consequently, individuals with a well-developed sense of personal dignity tend to devote considerable effort to maintaining and defending it throughout their lives (Malpas & Lickiss, 2007).

Consequently, low levels of self-control and excessive dependence on external influences and mechanisms of social control may threaten the development and maintenance of personal dignity. When Immanuel Kant emphasized the importance of autonomy, he referred precisely to an individual's capacity to regulate behavior through free will, self-control, and independent moral judgment rather than through dependence on external authorities or social pressures.

If individuals fail to progress to the higher stages of moral development described by Kohlberg and remain predominantly guided by social norms, public opinion, and external approval, their sense of self-respect and personal dignity may become increasingly vulnerable to external influences.

As individuals advance through the stages of moral development, they gradually develop their own moral principles, values, and ethical standards. Consequently, they become less dependent on external forms of social control and more capable of self-regulation. Because they increasingly assume personal responsibility for their actions and decisions, their behavior becomes guided by internalized values rather than external sanctions. In this respect, the development of self-control, moral autonomy, and personal responsibility constitutes an important foundation of personal dignity.

CHAPTER 2. PERSONAL DIGNITY AS A SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISM OF BEHAVIORAL REGULATION

2.1. The Nature of Personal Dignity as a Socio-Psychological Mechanism of Behavior

Human behavior in interpersonal relationships is inevitably influenced by personal dignity. Personal dignity develops through the process of socialization and gradually becomes one of the psychological mechanisms regulating behavior. Before examining its regulatory function, however, it is important to consider how personal dignity develops and which factors contribute to its formation.

One of the central components of personal dignity is self-esteem. The development of self-esteem is closely connected to the emergence of human needs and the individual's efforts to satisfy them. In this regard, Abraham Maslow's hierarchy of needs provides a useful theoretical framework. According to Maslow (1954), human needs are organized hierarchically, beginning with physiological and safety needs and progressing toward belongingness, esteem, and self-actualization. Lower-level needs must be sufficiently satisfied before higher-level needs become dominant motivational forces. Consequently, individuals who struggle to satisfy basic physiological or safety needs are less likely to focus on esteem-related concerns.

Adolescence is characterized by significant developments in self-awareness and self-evaluation. During this period, individuals seek acceptance, belonging, and meaningful relationships with peers. They often identify with particular groups that gradually become important reference groups, contributing to the satisfaction of belongingness and affiliation needs.

The emergence of self-esteem is closely associated with group membership and social identification. When individuals identify with a group and internalize its norms and values, they become increasingly concerned with their social standing and acceptance within that group. Being accepted and valued by others contributes positively to self-esteem and promotes a sense of personal worth.

Self-esteem represents an important psychological variable that influences multiple aspects of human functioning and is widely regarded as a prerequisite for healthy personality development. It affects how individuals think, feel, communicate, evaluate themselves, relate to others, and make important life decisions. Self-esteem also influences the capacity to give and receive love, adapt to challenges, and pursue personal growth.

Coopersmith (1967) conceptualized self-esteem as a learned pattern that develops through socialization. In his view, self-esteem emerges largely from the degree to which children perceive themselves as valued and respected by significant others, particularly their parents. Similarly, Rosenberg (1965) defined self-esteem as an individual's overall positive or negative evaluation of the self.

The Azerbaijani psychologist Akbar Bayramov (2003) emphasized that the need for self-esteem becomes particularly salient during adolescence as self-consciousness develops. Individuals seek recognition, respect, and approval from others, and these experiences contribute

to the formation of self-respect. Social recognition achieved through successful performance, social roles, or personal accomplishments strengthens both self-esteem and confidence in one's abilities.

The social origins of self-esteem can also be explained through Charles Cooley's concept of the *Looking-Glass Self*. According to Cooley (1922), individuals develop their self-concepts by imagining how they are perceived by others. George Herbert Mead (1972) further argued that what matters is not necessarily how others actually perceive us, but how we imagine their perceptions. Consequently, self-esteem develops within interpersonal relationships and social interactions.

When individuals are accepted and respected within their social groups, they tend to perceive themselves as valuable and worthy members of the community. Conversely, repeated experiences of rejection, ridicule, humiliation, or exclusion may lead individuals to perceive themselves as inadequate or unworthy. Persistent negative evaluations can contribute to feelings of inferiority and diminished self-esteem.

Alfred Adler's theory of personality development provides an additional perspective on this process. Adler (1956) viewed personality development as a response to feelings of inferiority and the striving for compensation. Individuals with chronically low self-esteem may develop an inferiority complex, which influences how they interpret social experiences and respond to interpersonal situations.

Coopersmith (1967) argued that self-esteem consists of evaluative beliefs individuals hold about themselves. According to this perspective, self-esteem reflects the degree to which individuals perceive themselves as competent, successful, capable, and worthy. In contrast, persistent feelings of inadequacy may undermine positive self-evaluation and contribute to psychological vulnerability (Güloğlu & Aydın, 2011). Because self-esteem represents one of the core components of personal dignity, the satisfaction of esteem needs contributes directly to the development of personal dignity. Individuals who feel valued, respected, and accepted are more likely to develop a strong sense of dignity and self-worth.

People with high self-esteem and a strong sense of personal dignity are generally more capable of establishing interpersonal boundaries and resisting behaviors that threaten their self-respect. They actively seek to protect their dignity when confronted with disrespect, humiliation, or exploitation. This raises an important question: why do some individuals demonstrate a strong capacity to defend their dignity while others appear more vulnerable to external influences?

To further explore this issue, it is useful to examine the life and legacy of Imadaddin Nasimi, whose commitment to personal convictions and human dignity has become a prominent symbol of dignity, self-respect, and moral courage in Azerbaijani cultural history.

Imadaddin Nasimi occupies a unique place in Azerbaijani intellectual and cultural history as a poet and thinker who emphasized the intrinsic worth, dignity, and spiritual potential of human beings (Nəsimi, 1973). In his writings, human beings are portrayed as possessing exceptional value and moral significance. Nasimi consistently highlighted virtues such as honor,

dignity, justice, integrity, and moral responsibility. His life is often interpreted as a powerful example of commitment to personal convictions and human dignity. Despite severe persecution and ultimately execution because of his beliefs, Nasimi refused to renounce his principles, thereby demonstrating extraordinary devotion to his ideals.

Similarly, Socrates is frequently regarded as an example of unwavering commitment to moral principles and personal dignity. The central concern of Socratic philosophy was the examination of human life, virtue, and ethical conduct. Through dialogue and critical questioning, Socrates encouraged individuals to reflect upon themselves, their values, and the assumptions underlying social conventions. His teachings were perceived as threatening by certain political and social authorities, ultimately resulting in his trial and death sentence. Nevertheless, Socrates chose to accept the legal consequences rather than abandon his principles, thereby illustrating the primacy of moral integrity over personal safety.

These examples raise an important question: what distinguished figures such as Nasimi and Socrates from most other individuals? The theoretical discussion presented in the previous chapter provides a possible answer. While most people possess a sense of personal dignity, only a limited number of individuals develop dignity into a stable personality characteristic. When dignity becomes integrated into the personality structure, it functions not merely as a moral emotion but as a guiding principle that shapes behavior, decision-making, and life goals. In such cases, dignity becomes a dominant motivational force capable of overriding concerns related to comfort, safety, or even survival.

This distinction is consistent with Allport's conception of cardinal traits. For certain individuals, dignity becomes a central organizing principle of personality. The actions of Nasimi, Socrates, Nelson Mandela, and Martin Luther King Jr. may be interpreted through this perspective, as their commitment to dignity and justice remained stable despite persecution, imprisonment, or the threat of death.

Skinner approached dignity from a different perspective, conceptualizing it as the social credit or recognition individuals receive for their actions. According to Skinner, behavior that contributes positively to society tends to be rewarded with approval, trust, and admiration. These social responses influence individuals' self-perceptions and contribute to the development of self-esteem and personal worth.

Skinner also argued that technological progress may reduce opportunities for individuals to demonstrate courage, responsibility, and competence. As technological systems increasingly prevent disasters and automate complex tasks, fewer situations require extraordinary acts of bravery or skill. Consequently, some traditional sources of social recognition and personal accomplishment may become less prominent in modern societies.

Within Maslow's hierarchy of needs, self-actualization occupies the highest level and represents the realization of an individual's fullest potential. Consequently, self-realization may be understood as an outcome of the satisfaction of self-actualization needs. The phenomenon of self-actualization has received considerable attention in Azerbaijani psychological literature and has been extensively discussed by scholars such as Bakhtiyar Aliyev and Rashid Jabbarov. Their

work emphasizes the role of self-actualization in personality development, psychological well-being, and the realization of individual capabilities (Əliyev, 1999, Cabbarov, 2004, 2008, 2010; Cabbarov & Əliyev, 2010).

The development of personal dignity is closely associated with self-actualization. According to Maslow, individuals become motivated by self-actualization only after lower-level physiological, safety, belongingness, and esteem needs have been sufficiently satisfied (Maware et al., 2016). Once these needs are fulfilled, individuals increasingly strive to realize their potential, pursue meaningful goals, and achieve a sense of fulfillment and purpose. In this regard, personal dignity may be viewed as both a prerequisite for and an outcome of self-actualization, as individuals who perceive themselves as valuable and capable are more likely to engage in activities that promote personal growth and self-realization.

The concepts of self-actualization, personal dignity, and value-based behavior may also be illustrated through the experiences of individuals who participated in the Second Karabakh War (2020). Although military behavior is influenced by numerous social, cultural, and situational factors, it provides an important context for understanding the relationship between personal values, identity, and human motivation.

A notable characteristic of the conflict was the participation of young individuals who had not previously experienced war but nevertheless volunteered to serve and defend their country. Alongside professional military personnel and conscripted soldiers, many citizens interrupted their education, employment, or family life in order to join the armed forces. From a psychological perspective, this phenomenon raises important questions concerning the motivational foundations of such behavior. To what extent can these actions be explained by patriotism, social identity, personal dignity, or self-actualization?

Maslow's hierarchy of needs offers one possible framework for understanding these motivations. At the most basic level, the protection of one's homeland and community may be associated with safety needs, which occupy the second level of Maslow's hierarchy (Zalova, 2019). The desire to preserve social stability, protect family members, and ensure collective security may therefore represent powerful motivational forces.

However, the experiences and narratives of many war veterans suggest that their actions cannot be explained solely through safety-related motives. Veterans frequently describe their participation in terms of honor, responsibility, pride, duty, and commitment to values larger than themselves. Such descriptions indicate the involvement of higher-order psychological needs, particularly esteem needs and self-actualization.

According to Maslow (1954), self-actualization involves the realization of one's potential and the pursuit of personally meaningful goals. Individuals who perceive their actions as serving a greater purpose often report feelings of fulfillment, usefulness, and personal significance. In this sense, participation in activities perceived as contributing to the welfare of one's community or nation may function as a source of self-esteem and self-actualization.

The concept of usefulness is also consistent with Adler's notion of striving for significance and social contribution. Individuals seek to perceive themselves as valuable

members of society whose actions have meaning and positive consequences for others. Acts of sacrifice, courage, and service may therefore strengthen self-respect and contribute to the development of personal dignity.

It is also important to recognize the role of socialization in the development of patriotic values. Family environments, educational institutions, cultural narratives, and collective historical memory contribute to the formation of national identity from an early age. Through these processes, values related to responsibility, collective belonging, and commitment to one's country become integrated into the individual's self-concept.

Consequently, the behavior displayed by many participants in the Second Karabakh War may be understood not only in terms of patriotism but also in relation to personal dignity, self-respect, and internalized moral values. In situations involving personal risk, individuals often act in accordance with deeply held beliefs regarding honor, responsibility, loyalty, and duty. Such behavior reflects the operation of internalized value systems rather than merely external social pressures.

From this perspective, personal dignity should not be viewed exclusively as an individual phenomenon. In collectivistic cultural contexts, dignity may also possess a social and national dimension, linking the individual's self-concept with broader forms of social identity and collective belonging. This broader manifestation may be conceptualized as **national dignity**, reflecting the relationship between personal dignity, national identity, and commitment to collective values.

Returning to Maslow's framework, self-actualization is closely associated with the realization of personal potential and the achievement of meaningful goals (Zalova, 2019). William James (1890a) similarly argued that self-esteem is dynamically determined by the relationship between aspirations and accomplishments. As individuals strive to realize their ideal selves, the successful attainment of personally significant goals contributes to self-respect, psychological well-being, and the experience of personal dignity.

James (1980a) proposed that self-esteem can be understood as the ratio between one's successes and one's aspirations. As he noted, where there is no aspiration, failure cannot occur; and where there is no failure, disappointment and frustration are absent. In this regard, self-esteem may be expressed through the following formula:

$$\text{Self-Esteem} = \text{Successes} / \text{Pretensions (Level of Aspiration)}$$

From this perspective, an individual's self-concept is shaped by the relationship between the ideal self and actual achievements. When aspirations greatly exceed accomplishments, self-esteem tends to decline. Conversely, successful attainment of personally meaningful goals strengthens self-respect and promotes a more positive self-evaluation. Therefore, realistic self-awareness, including an accurate understanding of one's abilities, limitations, and potential, represents an important prerequisite for healthy personality development and self-realization.

Research on self-actualization has consistently demonstrated that one of its fundamental conditions is the presence of psychological independence and personal autonomy (Cabbarov,

2008). This observation is closely related to the discussion of social control presented in the previous chapter. Self-actualizing individuals tend to rely on internal values and principles rather than excessive dependence on external approval or social pressure.

Although human behavior is inevitably influenced by social norms, laws, cultural expectations, and other forms of social control, excessive dependence on external regulation may hinder personal growth. Individuals whose behavior is determined primarily by external expectations often experience difficulties in achieving genuine autonomy and self-realization. In this regard, Skinner argued that when human behavior can be fully explained by external controlling factors, the concepts of freedom and dignity become increasingly problematic. Consequently, excessive reliance on social control may weaken the individual's sense of autonomy and personal dignity.

Based on these considerations, a dignified person may be described as an individual who possesses self-respect, fulfills social responsibilities conscientiously, and regulates behavior according to internalized moral principles rather than external pressures alone. Such individuals demonstrate autonomy, responsibility, and moral consistency across different situations. As personal dignity develops and becomes integrated into the individual's self-concept, the process of self-actualization becomes increasingly attainable.

Accordingly, the formation of personal dignity constitutes one of the key psychological conditions for self-realization and mature personality development. Because personal dignity and self-esteem are important components of the self-concept, the development of a coherent and positive sense of self facilitates the realization of individual potential and contributes to the achievement of self-actualization.

2.2. The Role of Personal Dignity in the Formation of Self-Concept

Throughout the process of socialization, self-respect and personal dignity, which develop through individuals' experiences of success and failure, play a significant role in the formation of self-consciousness. Self-consciousness is commonly described as comprising three interrelated components: self-concept, self-evaluation, and behavioral tendencies (Bayramov & Əlizadə, 2003). Among these components, the self-concept occupies a central position, as it reflects an individual's perceptions and beliefs about the self.

According to V. Stolin and A. Bodalev, self-concept develops through the process of self-knowledge and self-understanding. As individuals interact with their social environment, they acquire information about themselves, which gradually becomes integrated into their self-concept (Cabbarov, 2004).

One of the earliest and most influential theoretical accounts of the self was proposed by William James (1890). James distinguished between the "I" (the knowing self) and the "Me" (the known self) and identified several dimensions of the self, including the material self, social self, spiritual self, and pure ego. Of particular relevance is the spiritual self, which encompasses an individual's inner life, values, attitudes, abilities, and aspirations. James argued that individuals

often derive greater satisfaction from their moral and psychological qualities than from material possessions.

Subsequent theories further elaborated the multidimensional nature of self-concept. Higgins' Self-Discrepancy Theory distinguishes among the actual self, ideal self, and ought self (Higgins, 1987). The actual self refers to the attributes individuals believe they possess, the ideal self reflects the attributes they would like to possess, and the ought self represents the attributes they believe they should possess. Higgins proposed that discrepancies between these self-representations produce distinct emotional outcomes. Differences between the actual and ideal self are associated with disappointment and frustration, whereas discrepancies between the actual and ought self tend to generate anxiety, tension, and feelings of obligation.

The development of self-concept becomes particularly important during adolescence. Azerbaijani psychologist A. S. Bayramov and A. Alizade (2009) emphasized that adolescence is characterized by the emergence of self-awareness and self-respect as fundamental psychological needs. During this period, individuals become increasingly concerned with understanding their abilities, values, emotions, and social roles. As self-awareness develops, adolescents construct more complex representations of themselves and their place within the social world.

Similarly, Erik Erikson (1950) identified adolescence as a critical stage in the development of identity. During this period, individuals attempt to establish a coherent sense of self while adapting to new social relationships, expectations, and responsibilities. Peer relationships, group membership, and social acceptance become particularly important, contributing significantly to the formation of self-concept and personal identity.

Bakhtiyar Aliyev (1999) argued that individuals simultaneously construct an image of themselves and an image of the world. These two representations exist in a dynamic and reciprocal relationship: the way individuals perceive the world influences how they perceive themselves, while their self-perceptions shape their interpretation of social reality. Consequently, self-concept emerges through the interaction between personal experiences and the broader social environment.

Within this framework, personal dignity occupies an important position in the formation of self-concept. As individuals develop self-respect, moral values, and a sense of personal worth, these qualities become integrated into their understanding of who they are. Personal dignity therefore contributes not only to self-evaluation but also to the development of a stable and coherent self-concept. Individuals with a strong sense of personal dignity are more likely to perceive themselves as valuable, autonomous, and morally responsible persons, which in turn supports healthy identity development and psychological well-being (Чеснокова, 1977).

In addition to the cognitive aspects of self-concept, researchers have emphasized the importance of self-attitudes in personality development. V. Stolin (1983) distinguished between self-concept and self-attitude, arguing that while self-concept consists of an individual's beliefs and perceptions about the self, self-attitude represents a more stable evaluative orientation toward oneself. According to Stolin, self-concept includes both the characteristics individuals share with others and the attributes they perceive as unique to themselves.

Another important component of self-consciousness is self-evaluation. Azerbaijani psychologists A. Bayramov and A. Alizade (2003) argued that self-evaluation is closely associated with emotional experiences such as self-respect, self-love, and the preservation of personal dignity. Consequently, the development of self-esteem emerges through the process of evaluating one's abilities, achievements, personal qualities, and social roles.

The relationship between self-esteem and personal dignity has been widely examined in psychological literature. Coopersmith viewed self-esteem as a learned characteristic that develops through socialization and is strongly influenced by parent-child relationships (Güloğlu & Aydın, 2011). He emphasized the importance of parental warmth, consistent expectations, and respect for the child's individuality in fostering healthy self-esteem. Similarly, Rosenberg conceptualized self-esteem as a positive or negative attitude toward the self that is shaped by cultural, familial, and interpersonal experiences (Rosenberg, 1965; Von Der Haar, 2005).

During adolescence, self-evaluation becomes increasingly complex and subjective. As cognitive and social development progresses, individuals rely less on external standards and increasingly evaluate themselves according to internalized values, beliefs, and personal goals. Research by Safin and Dubrovina suggests that adolescents gradually develop a more subjective and reflective understanding of themselves, allowing them to assess their successes and failures more independently and realistically (Cabbarov, 2004).

Humanistic psychologist Carl Rogers (1961) considered the development of a positive self-concept to be dependent upon experiences of unconditional positive regard. Rogers defined self-concept as an organized system of perceptions regarding one's personal characteristics, abilities, relationships, and experiences. According to Rogers, psychological difficulties emerge when there is a significant discrepancy between an individual's self-concept and actual experiences. In contrast, acceptance, empathy, and supportive interpersonal relationships facilitate healthy self-esteem and positive self-development.

The social origins of self-concept were further emphasized by Charles Cooley (1922) and George Herbert Mead (1972). Cooley's concept of the "looking-glass self" suggests that individuals develop self-perceptions through their interpretations of how others perceive and evaluate them. Mead extended this perspective by arguing that it is not others' actual evaluations that matter most, but rather individuals' perceptions and interpretations of those evaluations. Thus, self-concept emerges through social interaction and the internalization of others' perspectives.

Taken together, these theoretical perspectives indicate that self-concept, self-esteem, and personal dignity develop through continuous interaction between individual experiences and the social environment. As individuals acquire greater self-awareness, evaluate their abilities and values, and internalize social feedback, they gradually construct a stable sense of self. Personal dignity occupies an important place within this process, serving as a psychological foundation for self-respect, autonomy, and positive self-evaluation.

George Herbert Mead further elaborated the social foundations of selfhood in *Mind, Self, and Society* (1972). He distinguished between the subjective self ("I") and the objective self

("Me"), arguing that the objective self emerges through social interaction and the internalization of others' attitudes, whereas the subjective self represents the individual's response to those social influences. According to Mead, one of the central questions of self-development is how individuals become objects to themselves. His answer emphasized the role of the social environment: individuals learn to evaluate themselves by adopting the perspectives of others and reflecting upon the reactions they receive during social interaction.

This perspective is consistent with symbolic interactionist approaches developed by Mead, Cooley, and later Stryker. From this viewpoint, social meanings are created and maintained through interaction, communication, and the interpretation of symbols. Language occupies a particularly important role because it enables individuals to interpret others' expectations and construct self-understanding. Consequently, self-concept develops not in isolation but through continuous engagement with significant others and the broader social environment.

Mead also emphasized the importance of social roles in the development of self-consciousness. During childhood, individuals begin to understand themselves by imitating adults and later by assuming different roles in play situations. Through role-taking, children learn to view themselves from the perspective of others, gradually differentiating the self from the external world. This process contributes to the emergence of self-awareness and provides the foundation for the development of self-concept.

The social origins of self-esteem can also be observed within educational settings. Research has consistently demonstrated that teachers' expectations influence students' academic achievement, motivation, and self-evaluations. This phenomenon is commonly referred to as the Pygmalion Effect or Rosenthal Effect (Rosenthal & Jacobson, 1968, 1992). Rosenthal and Jacobson proposed that higher expectations often lead to improved performance, whereas lower expectations may contribute to poorer outcomes. Teachers who expect success from particular students tend to provide greater encouragement, support, and learning opportunities, thereby increasing the likelihood that these students will succeed (Merton, 1968).

The influence of expectations extends beyond academic performance and affects students' self-esteem. Positive feedback and successful experiences contribute to a more favorable self-concept, whereas repeated experiences of failure may undermine self-confidence and self-worth (Myers, 2008). In this regard, William James argued that self-esteem depends upon the relationship between achievements and aspirations. Individuals evaluate themselves by comparing their actual accomplishments with their desired goals and standards (Durmuş, 2017). When achievements correspond to aspirations, self-esteem tends to increase; when aspirations substantially exceed accomplishments, feelings of disappointment and reduced self-worth may emerge.

The relationship between self-esteem and achievement is reciprocal. Academic success contributes to positive self-evaluations, while higher self-esteem enhances motivation, persistence, and subsequent achievement. Furthermore, self-regulation plays an important role in this process. Students with well-developed self-control are more likely to fulfill their academic

responsibilities, maintain goal-directed behavior, and achieve positive outcomes. These experiences, in turn, strengthen self-esteem and contribute to a more positive and coherent self-concept.

From the perspective of the present study, personal dignity occupies an important place within this developmental process. As individuals internalize social feedback, develop self-respect, and construct a stable sense of self, personal dignity becomes integrated into their self-concept. Consequently, dignity functions not only as a moral value but also as a psychological resource that supports self-respect, autonomy, and positive self-evaluation.

Undoubtedly, each of these factors contributes to individuals' self-realization and self-development within educational settings. The problem of self-actualization in the context of education has been extensively examined by numerous scholars, including A. Bayramov, A. Alizadeh, B. Aliyev, R. Gadirova, R. Ibrahimbayova, E. Shafiyeva, L. Jabbarova, M. Mustafayev, R. Jabbarov, A. Maslow, G. Allport, G. H. Mead, C. H. Cooley, B. Ananyev, and D. Leontiev. Collectively, these studies emphasize the importance of educational experiences in fostering self-awareness, self-esteem, personal growth, and the realization of individual potential.

From this perspective, promoting self-awareness and healthy self-esteem among adolescents and young adults requires educational environments that encourage creativity, autonomy, and active participation. Educational practices grounded in humanistic principles are particularly important because they support students' personal development while facilitating the formation of positive self-concepts.

The theoretical perspectives reviewed in this chapter suggest that personal dignity is closely associated with self-esteem and plays a significant role in the development of self-concept. As noted previously, self-concept consists of individuals' beliefs, perceptions, and evaluations regarding themselves. These self-perceptions are continuously shaped through experiences of success and failure, which influence self-evaluation and, consequently, self-esteem. As self-esteem increases, individuals tend to develop a stronger sense of personal dignity, which further contributes to a more positive perception of themselves.

This relationship appears to be reciprocal in nature. Individuals' existing self-perceptions influence their behavior and goal-directed activities, while the outcomes of those activities subsequently modify self-evaluation, self-esteem, and personal dignity. These changes, in turn, contribute to the reorganization and development of self-concept. Because self-esteem represents both a central component of self-consciousness and an important component of personal dignity, personal dignity may be regarded as a significant psychological factor contributing to the formation and development of self-concept.

Accordingly, personal dignity should be understood not merely as a moral value but also as a psychological construct that supports positive self-evaluation, self-respect, and the development of a coherent and stable sense of self.

CHAPTER 3. AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION OF THE SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PERSONAL DIGNITY

3.1. Research Design and Procedure

Participants

The study was conducted between 2019 and 2021 and involved undergraduate and graduate students from four higher education institutions in Azerbaijan: Baku State University, Azerbaijan Medical University, Azerbaijan Technical University, and Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University. Participants were selected using a convenience sampling strategy. Participation was voluntary, and all respondents provided informed consent prior to data collection.

A total of 192 students participated in the study. To ensure comparability across educational levels, an equal number of participants was recruited from each academic group. The sample consisted of six groups representing different stages of higher education: first-, second-, third-, and fourth-year undergraduate students, as well as first- and second-year graduate students. Each group included 32 participants.

Of the total sample, 42 participants (21.9%) were male and 150 participants (78.1%) were female. Participants were selected on a voluntary basis and provided informed consent prior to participation. Data were collected using standardized psychological instruments assessing self-esteem, self-evaluation, and moral development.

The sample was specifically selected to examine age-related and educational-level differences in the development of personal dignity and its associations with self-esteem and moral characteristics among university students.

Measures

Assessment of Moral Development was assessed using a multidimensional methodology designed to evaluate three interrelated components of moral functioning:

1. Knowledge of moral qualities;
2. Attitudes toward moral qualities;
3. Behavioral manifestation of moral qualities.

The assessment focused on six moral characteristics: humanism, patriotism, collectivism, tolerance, dignity, and industriousness.

The knowledge component evaluated participants' understanding of each moral quality. Responses were scored according to the degree of conceptual clarity and completeness.

The attitude component assessed the subjective importance attributed to each moral quality using a three-point rating scale.

The behavioral component measured the frequency with which each moral quality was reflected in participants' everyday behavior. Composite scores were calculated for each moral

quality by averaging scores across the three dimensions. Higher scores indicated a higher level of moral development.

Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale. Participants' self-esteem was assessed using the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES). The scale consists of ten items evaluating global self-worth and self-acceptance. Responses are rated on a four-point Likert scale ranging from strong disagreement to strong agreement. Higher total scores indicate higher levels of self-esteem, whereas lower scores reflect reduced self-worth and negative self-evaluation.

Dembo–Rubinstein Self-Evaluation Method. This method assesses individuals' perceptions of themselves across several personally significant dimensions.

Participants evaluated their perceived standing on visual analogue scales representing:

- Intelligence;
- Self-confidence;
- Peer authority;
- Physical attractiveness.

Higher positions on the scales reflected more positive self-evaluations. The method enabled the assessment of both the level and structure of participants' self-perceptions.

Procedure

Data collection was conducted in group settings during scheduled sessions. All instruments were administered under standardized conditions to minimize the influence of situational variables.

Participants first completed the Moral Development Assessment, followed by the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale and the Dembo–Rubinstein Self-Evaluation Method. The order of administration was kept constant across participants to ensure procedural consistency.

Following completion of the questionnaires, brief discussions were conducted with participants to obtain additional qualitative insights regarding their self-perceptions and evaluations.

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted in accordance with ethical principles governing psychological research. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were informed about the purpose of the study before participation.

Participants were assured that their responses would remain anonymous and confidential and would be used exclusively for scientific purposes. No personally identifiable information was collected.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were calculated for all study variables, including means, standard deviations, and score distributions.

Pearson correlation analyses were conducted to examine the relationships among personal dignity, moral development, self-esteem, and self-evaluation. Group differences across years of study were analyzed using appropriate inferential statistical procedures.

The statistical analyses were performed using standard quantitative research software. Statistical significance was evaluated at the .05 level.

3.2. Analysis and Interpretation of the Findings

The present study was based on the assumption that personal dignity constitutes a fundamental psychological characteristic that contributes to the development of other moral qualities among university students.

Developmental differences associated with educational level were adopted as the primary criterion of comparison. To ensure methodological consistency, an equal number of participants was selected from each academic level. The total sample consisted of 192 students, with 32 participants representing each academic group. Of the participants, 42 were male and 150 were female.

The findings obtained from all three assessment instruments were analyzed and interpreted. In addition, correlation analyses were conducted using statistical software to examine the relationships among the studied variables.

The study was implemented in several stages. First, comparisons across academic levels were performed using the nonparametric Mann–Whitney U test. The results are presented in the following tables and figures.

Table 3.1. Comparison of Moral Qualities Between First- and Third-Year Undergraduate Students

Statistical Indicators	Humanism	Patriotism	Collectivism	Tolerance	Dignity	Diligence
Mann–Whitney U	407.0	408.5	499.5	467.5	366.5	418.0
Wilcoxon W	935.0	936.5	1027.5	995.5	894.5	946.0
Z	-1.467	-1.424	-0.171	-0.610	-2.077	-1.300
p (two-tailed)	.142	.154	.864	.542	.038	.194

Note. *p* values are based on two-tailed significance tests. Statistical significance was observed only for *Personal Dignity* ($p = .038$), indicating a significant difference between first- and third-year students on this dimension.

The results presented in Table 3.1 indicate that, among the examined moral qualities, a statistically significant difference emerged only for the dignity dimension ($U = 366.5$, $Z =$

-2.077, $p = .038$). No statistically significant differences were observed for humanism, patriotism, collectivism, tolerance, or industriousness ($p > .05$).

Examination of the mean rank scores revealed that first-year students obtained a mean rank of 28.00 on the dignity dimension, whereas third-year students obtained a mean rank of 37.00. These findings indicate significantly higher dignity scores among third-year students compared to first-year students. Although the cross-sectional nature of the study does not permit causal conclusions, the results suggest that dignity-related characteristics may become more pronounced across the course of university education.

Table 3.2. Comparison of Moral Qualities Between Second- and Fourth-Year Undergraduate Students

Statistical Criteria	Humanism	Patriotism	Collectivism	Tolerance	Dignity	Industriousness
Mann–Whitney U	421.5	297.0	469.5	448.0	487.0	477.5
Wilcoxon W	949.5	825.0	997.5	976.0	1015.0	1005.5
Z	-1.270	-2.958	-0.587	-0.875	-0.346	-0.482
Asym.Sig. (2-tailed)	.204	.003	.557	.382	.729	.630

The results presented in Table 3.2 indicate that a statistically significant difference was observed only for the patriotism dimension ($U = 297.0$, $Z = -2.958$, $p = .003$). No significant differences were found for humanism, collectivism, tolerance, dignity, or industriousness ($p > .05$).

Examination of the mean rank scores revealed that second-year students obtained a mean rank of 39.22 on the patriotism dimension, whereas fourth-year students obtained a mean rank of 25.78. These findings indicate significantly higher patriotism scores among second-year students compared to fourth-year students. Although the cross-sectional design does not allow causal inferences, the results suggest that the expression of patriotic attitudes may vary across different stages of university education.

Table 3.3. Comparison of Moral Qualities Between Second-Year Undergraduate Students and First-Year Graduate Students

Statistical Criteria	Humanism	Patriotism	Collectivism	Tolerance	Dignity	Industriousness
Mann–Whitney U	468.0	289.5	511.5	360.0	478.5	444.5

Wilcoxon W	996.0	817.5	1039.5	888.0	1006.5	972.5
Z	-0.620	-3.093	-0.007	-2.101	-0.469	-0.947
Asym.Sig. (2-tailed)	.535	.002	.995	.036	.639	.344

As presented in Table 3.3, statistically significant differences were observed between second-year undergraduate students and first-year graduate students with respect to patriotism and tolerance. Consistent with the findings reported in the previous comparison, patriotism scores were significantly higher among second-year undergraduate students (Mean Rank = 39.45) than among first-year graduate students (Mean Rank = 25.55), indicating a decline in patriotism-related characteristics across educational levels.

In contrast, tolerance scores demonstrated the opposite pattern. Second-year undergraduate students obtained a mean rank of 27.75, whereas first-year graduate students obtained a mean rank of 37.25. This finding suggests that tolerance tends to increase as students advance through higher levels of education.

Taken together, these results indicate a decreasing trend in patriotism and an increasing trend in tolerance across successive stages of academic development.

Table 3.4. Comparison of Moral Qualities Between Second-Year Undergraduate Students and Second-Year Graduate Students

Statistical Criteria	Humanism	Patriotism	Collectivism	Tolerance	Dignity	Industriousness
Mann–Whitney U	434.0	383.0	455.5	370.0	461.5	473.0
Wilcoxon W	962.0	911.0	983.5	898.0	989.5	1001.0
Z	-1.107	-1.799	-0.783	-1.957	-0.711	-0.546
Asym.Sig. (2-tailed)	.268	.072	.434	.050	.477	.585

Table 3.4 presents the comparison between second-year undergraduate students and second-year graduate students. Among the six moral qualities examined, only tolerance approached statistical significance ($p = .050$). Examination of mean rank scores revealed that second-year undergraduate students obtained a mean rank of 28.06, whereas second-year graduate students obtained a mean rank of 36.94. These findings suggest that tolerance-related characteristics become more pronounced at more advanced stages of higher education.

Table 3.5. Comparison of Moral Qualities Between Third-Year and Fourth-Year Undergraduate Students

Statistical Criteria	Humanism	Patriotism	Collectivism	Tolerance	Dignity	Industriousness
Mann–Whitney U	480.5	335.0	424.0	452.0	432.5	501.0
Wilcoxon W	1008.5	863.0	952.0	980.0	960.5	1029.0
Z	-0.444	-2.426	-1.223	-0.822	-1.107	-0.154
Asym.Sig. (2-tailed)	.657	.015	.221	.411	.268	.878

As shown in Table 3.5, a statistically significant difference was identified only for patriotism. Third-year students obtained a higher mean rank (38.03) than fourth-year students (26.97), indicating that patriotism scores were significantly lower among fourth-year students.

The repeated emergence of significant differences in patriotism across several educational comparisons suggests a systematic association between academic progression and patriotism-related characteristics. Specifically, the findings indicate a gradual decline in patriotism scores as students advance through higher levels of education. Given the consistency of this pattern across multiple comparisons, further theoretical and empirical examination is warranted to better understand the developmental, social, and educational factors that may contribute to these changes.

Table 3.6. Comparison of Moral Qualities Between Third-Year Undergraduate Students and First-Year Graduate Students

Statistical Criteria	Humanism	Patriotism	Collectivism	Tolerance	Dignity	Industriousness
Mann–Whitney U	438.5	333.0	470.0	480.0	420.5	490.0
Wilcoxon W	966.5	861.0	998.0	1008.0	948.5	1018.0
Z	-1.027	-2.472	-0.586	-0.443	-1.303	-0.308
Asym.Sig. (2-tailed)	.304	.013	.558	.658	.193	.758

As shown in Table 3.6, a statistically significant difference emerged only for patriotism ($p = .013$). Examination of mean rank scores indicated that third-year undergraduate students

obtained a higher patriotism score (Mean Rank = 38.09) than first-year graduate students (Mean Rank = 26.91). Consistent with the findings reported in previous comparisons, patriotism scores demonstrated a gradual decline across successive educational levels. The consistency of this pattern suggests that educational progression may be associated with changes in patriotism-related attitudes and values, warranting further investigation.

Table 3.7. Correlations Among Moral Qualities

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Humanism	—					
2. Patriotism	.152*	—				
3. Collectivism	.322**	.121*	—			
4. Tolerance	.196**	.087	.271**	—		
5. Personal Dignity	.220**	.177**	.275**	.252**	—	
6. Industriousness	.227**	.279**	.350**	.165*	.361**	—

Note. $p < .05$; $p < .01$.

The correlation analysis revealed significant positive associations among most of the moral qualities examined. Humanism was positively correlated with patriotism ($r = .152, p < .05$), collectivism ($r = .322, p < .01$), tolerance ($r = .196, p < .01$), dignity ($r = .220, p < .01$), and industriousness ($r = .227, p < .01$).

Patriotism was positively associated with humanism ($r = .152, p < .05$), collectivism ($r = .121, p < .05$), dignity ($r = .177, p < .01$), and industriousness ($r = .279, p < .01$). However, its relationship with tolerance was not statistically significant.

Of particular importance for the present study were the correlations involving dignity. The findings demonstrated that dignity was positively and significantly associated with all other moral qualities, including humanism ($r = .220, p < .01$), patriotism ($r = .177, p < .01$), collectivism ($r = .275, p < .01$), tolerance ($r = .252, p < .01$), and industriousness ($r = .361, p < .01$). Among these relationships, the strongest association was observed between dignity and industriousness.

Overall, these findings support the central assumption of the present research that personal dignity occupies an important position within the broader system of moral qualities and is positively related to a wide range of socially desirable characteristics.

Analysis of the Dembo–Rubinstein Self-Evaluation Method

In the second stage of the analysis, the results obtained from the Dembo–Rubinstein Self-Evaluation Method were examined. This instrument was used to investigate the discrepancy

between students' perceived current characteristics (real self) and their desired characteristics (ideal self) across several domains.

Intelligence. Analysis of the intelligence criterion indicated that students generally evaluated their current intellectual abilities relatively positively. Although some variation was observed across academic levels, substantial differences in self-evaluated intelligence were not evident.

A more notable finding emerged when examining aspiration levels. Across all educational groups, participants reported higher desired levels of intelligence than their current self-evaluations, suggesting the presence of self-improvement goals. However, the discrepancy between the real and ideal self remained within a relatively moderate range. The largest discrepancies were observed among first-year undergraduate students and first-year graduate students, indicating comparatively stronger aspirations and higher expectations regarding their intellectual development.

These findings suggest that while students generally maintain a positive perception of their intellectual abilities, younger and newly enrolled students may display somewhat more idealized self-perceptions and achievement expectations.

Self-Confidence. The analysis of self-confidence demonstrated that its developmental pattern was not strictly linear across academic levels. Both increases and decreases were observed throughout the educational trajectory.

The highest levels of self-confidence were found among third- and fourth-year undergraduate students, whereas the lowest levels were observed among first-year undergraduate students. Furthermore, first-year students demonstrated the largest discrepancy between their real and ideal self-confidence scores. This substantial gap may reflect uncertainty associated with adaptation to university life, identity development, and adjustment to new academic and social environments.

In contrast, the relatively smaller discrepancy observed among third- and fourth-year students suggests a greater alignment between self-perceptions and aspirations, reflecting a more stable and realistic self-concept.

Physical Appearance. With regard to physical appearance, first-year undergraduate students exhibited the largest discrepancy between their current and desired appearance. This finding parallels the results obtained for self-confidence and may indicate that concerns about physical appearance contribute to lower self-confidence during the initial stages of university education.

In contrast, second- and third-year students reported more moderate aspiration levels and smaller discrepancies between real and ideal appearance. Notably, third-year students demonstrated the smallest discrepancy, suggesting greater satisfaction with their physical appearance and a more realistic self-evaluation.

Taken together, the findings related to intelligence, self-confidence, and physical appearance indicate that discrepancies between the real and ideal self tend to decrease as students progress through higher education. This pattern may reflect increasing self-awareness, more

realistic self-evaluations, and greater psychological adjustment during the course of academic development.

3.3. Social-Psychological Characteristics of the Development of Personal Dignity

The findings of the present study suggest that students' self-evaluations vary across different stages of higher education. Although it might be expected that self-evaluation becomes progressively more accurate as students advance through university, the obtained results indicate a more complex developmental pattern. Self-evaluation scores were relatively low among first-year undergraduate students, increased during the third and fourth years of study, and then showed a slight decline among graduate students.

Several explanations may account for this pattern. First-year students generally possess less academic experience and fewer opportunities for self-reflection regarding their abilities and achievements. Furthermore, the transition from adolescence to emerging adulthood is accompanied by ongoing identity formation and self-concept development, which may contribute to less stable and less accurate self-evaluations.

A particularly noteworthy finding was that third-year students demonstrated the most positive self-attitudes. Compared to students in other academic years, they exhibited a smaller discrepancy between their aspirations and their perceived actual achievements. This pattern suggests a higher degree of congruence between self-perception and reality. At this stage, students appear to evaluate their knowledge, competencies, and abilities more realistically, reflecting a more mature and integrated self-concept.

The slight decline observed among senior undergraduate and graduate students may be explained by increasing concerns regarding future career opportunities, professional responsibilities, and life goals. As students approach graduation, uncertainty about future employment and personal development may influence their self-evaluations despite their accumulated knowledge and achievements.

Because personal dignity is closely associated with individuals' perceptions and evaluations of themselves, the manner in which students construct and maintain self-attitudes may significantly influence the development of their sense of personal dignity.

Relationship Between Personal Dignity and Self-Esteem. To examine the association between personal dignity and self-esteem, a Spearman rank-order correlation analysis was conducted. The results are presented in Table 3.8.

Table 3.8. Correlation Between Personal Dignity and Self-Esteem

Variable	1	2
1. Self-Esteem	—	.827**
2. Personal Dignity	.827**	—

Note. Spearman's rho correlation coefficients are reported. $p = .003$.

The results revealed a strong positive correlation between self-esteem and personal dignity ($\rho = .827$, $p = .003$). This finding indicates that students who report higher levels of self-esteem also tend to report higher levels of personal dignity. The magnitude of the relationship suggests that these constructs are closely interconnected while remaining conceptually distinct.

The observed relationship is consistent with theoretical perspectives emphasizing the role of self-evaluation processes in the development of personal dignity. Individuals who possess a positive evaluation of their own worth are more likely to perceive themselves as deserving respect and recognition, which constitutes a central component of personal dignity.

The findings also support developmental theories of self-esteem. According to William James, self-esteem is influenced by the relationship between aspirations and achievements. Graduate students generally possess greater educational experience, more developed competencies, and a broader history of accomplishments than first-year undergraduates, which may contribute to their higher levels of self-esteem and, consequently, their stronger sense of personal dignity.

An additional finding of the study concerns students' understanding of moral qualities. Although participants generally reported positive attitudes toward moral characteristics and evaluated their own behavior favorably, many experienced difficulty defining and describing the conceptual meaning of these qualities. For example, a substantial proportion of students interpreted tolerance primarily as the ability to endure difficulties and remain psychologically strong rather than as acceptance and respect for diversity. This finding suggests that positive attitudes toward moral values do not necessarily imply a sophisticated conceptual understanding of those values.

Overall, the results indicate that personal dignity develops in conjunction with broader processes of self-evaluation, self-esteem, and identity formation. As students progress through higher education, changes in self-perception and self-esteem appear to contribute significantly to the formation and maintenance of personal dignity.

Further analysis revealed that students' scores on moral qualities tended to increase slightly across academic years. Although the observed differences were generally modest, the findings suggest a gradual development of moral characteristics throughout higher education.

An interesting finding emerged regarding students' conceptual understanding of moral values. Many participants experienced difficulty defining and explaining concepts such as dignity, humanism, and tolerance. Several students explicitly reported that they had rarely reflected on the meaning of personal dignity before participating in the study. This observation suggests that positive attitudes toward moral values do not necessarily imply a well-developed conceptual understanding of those values.

In describing the concept of dignity, many students referred to notions such as honor, morality, integrity, and personal reputation. These responses indicate that students' perceptions of dignity are strongly influenced by the cultural and moral values prevalent within Azerbaijani

society. Thus, the understanding of dignity appears to be embedded within a broader framework of national and cultural traditions.

The correlation analysis presented in Table 3.7 demonstrated that personal dignity was the only moral characteristic significantly associated with all other moral qualities included in the study. Positive correlations were observed between personal dignity and humanism, patriotism, collectivism, tolerance, and industriousness. This finding suggests that personal dignity may function as an integrative moral construct that develops in conjunction with other moral characteristics. Moreover, the results support the assumption that dignity occupies a central position within the structure of students' moral development.

Another noteworthy finding concerned the relationship between academic year and patriotism. The results indicated a slight negative association between educational level and patriotism scores, suggesting that patriotic attitudes tended to decrease as students progressed through higher education. One possible explanation for this pattern may be found in Kohlberg's theory of moral development.

According to Kohlberg, moral judgments in earlier developmental stages are primarily based on conformity to social norms, authority, and culturally accepted standards. As individuals mature, however, they increasingly rely on autonomous moral reasoning and personal principles. From this perspective, younger students may evaluate patriotism primarily through values acquired from family, school, and social institutions, whereas older students may adopt a more individualized and reflective approach to issues related to national identity and citizenship. Consequently, differences in patriotism scores across academic years may reflect developmental changes in moral reasoning rather than a decline in commitment to national values.

Particular attention should also be given to the relationship between patriotism and personal dignity. During data collection, many students associated patriotism with national events, collective historical experiences, and symbols of national identity. These responses suggest that patriotic attitudes among young people are closely connected to collective memory and sociocultural experiences.

From a social-psychological perspective, the association between patriotism and personal dignity may be understood through the concept of social identity. Within many cultural contexts, individuals often perceive service to their community, commitment to collective welfare, and responsibility toward society as important components of personal dignity. Therefore, dignity is not perceived solely as an individual characteristic related to self-respect but also as a value connected to group membership, collective identity, and social responsibility.

Taken together, these findings suggest that personal dignity represents a multidimensional construct that incorporates self-respect, moral values, social responsibility, and identification with broader social and cultural communities. Students who demonstrate higher levels of dignity tend to exhibit stronger moral orientations across multiple domains, supporting the proposition that personal dignity plays a central role in moral development during emerging adulthood.

CONCLUSION

The present study examined the social-psychological characteristics of personal dignity among university students and explored the factors contributing to its development. The findings indicate that personal dignity represents a central component of students' moral and psychological functioning. Significant positive associations were observed between personal dignity and several moral qualities, including humanism, patriotism, collectivism, tolerance, and industriousness. Furthermore, personal dignity demonstrated a strong positive relationship with self-esteem, supporting the assumption that positive self-evaluation plays an important role in the development of a dignified sense of self.

The results also suggest that personal dignity is closely connected to self-concept formation, self-regulation, and responsible behavior. Individuals with a stronger sense of personal dignity appear more likely to internalize moral standards and regulate their behavior independently of external control. Overall, the findings support the view that personal dignity constitutes a multidimensional construct that contributes to students' personal, moral, and social development.

Theoretical Contributions

This study contributes to the literature on personal dignity by integrating perspectives from social psychology, personality psychology, and moral development. The findings provide empirical support for theoretical approaches that conceptualize dignity as a psychological construct associated with self-esteem, self-concept, and moral values.

In addition, the study demonstrates that personal dignity is not an isolated personal characteristic but rather a construct embedded within a broader system of moral qualities. The observed associations between dignity and humanism, patriotism, collectivism, tolerance, and industriousness suggest that dignity may serve as an organizing principle within the moral structure of personality.

The findings further contribute to developmental perspectives by showing that personal dignity varies across different stages of higher education and is associated with age-related changes in self-perception and moral reasoning.

Practical Implications

The results have several practical implications for higher education and youth development programs. Universities may contribute to the development of students' personal dignity through educational practices that promote self-reflection, self-awareness, ethical reasoning, and social responsibility.

The findings also suggest that interventions aimed at strengthening self-esteem and positive self-concept may indirectly contribute to the development of personal dignity. Educational and psychological support programs designed to enhance students' confidence, resilience, and self-understanding may therefore foster broader positive developmental outcomes.

Furthermore, the strong associations between dignity and moral qualities indicate that dignity-related competencies may be incorporated into character education, citizenship education, and personal development initiatives within higher education settings.

Limitations

Several limitations should be acknowledged when interpreting the findings of this study. First, the research employed a cross-sectional design, which limits the ability to draw causal conclusions regarding the developmental processes underlying personal dignity.

Second, the sample consisted exclusively of university students, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings to other age groups or social populations. Future studies should include more diverse samples representing different educational, occupational, and cultural backgrounds.

Third, the study relied primarily on self-report measures. Although self-report instruments provide valuable information regarding subjective experiences, they may also be influenced by social desirability and response biases.

Finally, the cultural context of Azerbaijan may have influenced participants' understanding of concepts such as dignity, patriotism, and moral responsibility. Consequently, caution should be exercised when generalizing the findings to other sociocultural settings.

Directions for Future Research

Future research should investigate personal dignity using longitudinal designs in order to better understand its developmental trajectory across different life stages. Such studies would provide stronger evidence regarding the causal relationships between dignity, self-esteem, and moral development.

Further research may also examine the role of family relationships, educational experiences, peer influences, and cultural values in the formation of personal dignity. Exploring these factors could contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the social and psychological mechanisms underlying dignity development.

In addition, future studies should investigate personal dignity in different cultural contexts and compare its structure and correlates across societies. Cross-cultural research may help clarify the extent to which personal dignity reflects universal psychological processes versus culturally specific value systems.

Finally, the development and validation of contemporary psychometric instruments specifically designed to assess personal dignity may represent an important direction for future research and contribute to the advancement of empirical studies in this field.

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ABSTRACT

Personal dignity represents an important psychological construct associated with self-respect, self-esteem, moral development, and the regulation of human behavior. Despite growing scholarly interest in dignity, relatively little empirical research has examined its socio-psychological characteristics among university students. The present study aimed to investigate the developmental dynamics of personal dignity and its relationships with self-esteem, self-evaluation, and moral qualities among university students in Azerbaijan.

The study employed a cross-sectional design involving 192 undergraduate and graduate students recruited from several higher education institutions. Data were collected using the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, the Dembo–Rubinstein Self-Evaluation Method, and a Moral Development Assessment measuring humanism, patriotism, collectivism, tolerance, dignity, and industriousness. Descriptive statistics, Mann–Whitney U tests, and correlation analyses were used to examine developmental differences and associations among the study variables.

The findings indicated that personal dignity was positively associated with all examined moral qualities. Significant positive correlations were observed between personal dignity and humanism, patriotism, collectivism, tolerance, and industriousness, suggesting that dignity occupies a central position within the moral structure of personality. The strongest association was found between dignity and industriousness. In addition, a strong positive relationship was identified between personal dignity and self-esteem, supporting theoretical assumptions regarding the role of self-evaluation in the development of dignity. Comparisons across educational levels revealed significant differences in personal dignity, patriotism, and tolerance, indicating that certain moral characteristics vary across stages of higher education.

The results suggest that personal dignity functions as an important socio-psychological mechanism underlying self-regulation, moral development, and positive self-concept formation. Furthermore, the findings highlight the role of self-esteem and social experiences in shaping dignity during emerging adulthood. The study contributes to the growing literature on dignity by providing empirical evidence regarding its developmental characteristics and psychological correlates among university students and offers practical implications for educational programs aimed at promoting students' personal and moral development.

Keywords: personal dignity, self-esteem, moral development, self-concept, university students, social psychology.